

FUTURE MILITARY AVIONICS APPLICATIONS OF WAFER-SCALE TECHNOLOGY
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ABSTRACT

WSI technology has the potential to substantially improve avionics system reliability and enable the development of airborne-compatible supercomputers for real-time machine intelligence and new forms of sensor integration. Companion technologies in the areas of advanced packaging, cooling and photonics will need to be integrated with WSI in order to achieve these goals. This paper describes the potential use of flyable wafer-based supercomputers for extremely high throughput applications. A description of these applications and associated processing requirements is also presented.

INTRODUCTION

This paper addresses the issue of the potential impact of WSI technology on future military avionics. In making this determination, it is imperative that fundamental issues regarding future avionics challenges, drivers and constraints that could be affected by WSI be identified. We need to then weigh the pros and cons of preliminary WSI designs for projected applications to see whether WSI technology, on balance, can provide significant improvements.

Is WSI fundamentally a superior and different technology for avionics, worthy of a focused effort involving significant investments in new materials and process development, packaging and cooling? Or, is WSI just another type of microcircuit design that is part of a continuum of improvements that have occurred in digital technology since the 1950s? Hopefully this paper will allow the reader to formulate a more informed opinion on this issue.

MILITARY AVIONICS PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITIES

There are several fundamental problems facing military avionics today that could be impacted by WSI technology. These problems are briefly described below:

Lack of Aircrew Situation Awareness

One of the basic functions of avionics is to provide internal and external situation awareness to the aircrew. Situation awareness, or simply "SA" is considered by many crew members as the single most important attribute they can possess. It is the awareness of the "Big Picture." It is information about threats, targets, friends and his own system that affect him in a time or space over which some control needs to be exerted.

However, aircrews are becoming inundated by an array of alphanumeric and sensor data that is causing them to "drown in data and starve for information". We are currently witnessing a paradoxical situation where the continued addition of avionics to enable improvements in SA is resulting in the reduction of SA, leading ultimately to a point of "diminishing returns" where the crew is unable to fully exploit the capability of the avionics and weapons to negate threats and targets. No single solution will provide SA. Instead, an integrated set of technologies must be used including larger full color displays, improved pictorial graphics and expert systems (AI) to reduce/distill data into information for presentation, provide "expert-reasoned" options in time-stressful situations and automation assistance to identify threats and targets. In addition, improved automation in vehicle control and weapon deployment is needed. All these technologies are under development at the Avionics Laboratory at Wright - Patterson. Machine intelligence however provides the greatest challenges and opportunities for both software and hardware. This area represents a particular opportunity for the employment of WSI technology.

Machine intelligence must be accomplished in real-time for military avionics (here, real-time means "fast enough" so that the crew does not have a noticeable wait for the result). For example, "simple" expert systems (e.g. display manager) will likely require a few hundreds of million operations per second (MOPS) for real-time operation. Automatic Target Recognizers (ATR) will need to operate at 5-10 billion operations per second (BOPS). Advanced signal processing to support Low Probability of Intercept (LPI) operation requires similar processing speeds. Approximately twenty applications requiring a 100 MOPS to a "few BOPS" of processing speeds are currently being investigated under an Avionics Laboratory contract with Westinghouse Electric Corporation, Baltimore, Maryland. This effort will determine speed, memory, I/O and algorithm requirements and will provide preliminary processor designs. Figure 1 shows examples of some of these applications with initial estimates of the required speeds.

Flyable, supercomputer-like processing speeds will be needed to execute the machine intelligence processes in real-time. Expected evolutionary improvements in chip level or multi-chip packaging will likely prove inadequate from the perspectives of weight, volume, electrical power and cooling requirements. Further, projected processors speed improvements that are expected because of feature size reduction (e.g. 0.5 micron) with a concomitant increase in clock speed (100 MHz limit) fall far short of the speed goals cited above. For example, uniprocessor speed is expected to peak at about 20 MIPs for a machine executing a complex instruction set such as the DAIS instruction mix and 100 MIPs for an ideal RISC mix.

Parallel processing will be required for most of these robust applications. Because of the need to tightly couple the processing nodes in order to achieve the above cited speeds, the nodes must be packaged in immediate proximity to reduce inter-nodal communication delays.

When one combines the requirements of low weight, volume and power with extremely high speed circuitry, only "hybrid" or WSI technology remains in contention. In building high speed parallel networks to achieve "supercomputer-like" speeds in a small volume, an excellent algorithm/architecture match is mandatory. [1] That is, the characteristics of the algorithm (whether it be for control, signal, image or AI processing applications) must permit decomposition such that when the separate parts are executed in parallel, a near linear speed up is achieved. Thus, one

needs to postulate wafer-based designs, single or stacked, that range from a few nodes (say five or so for control applications such as advanced engine control for thrust vectored engines having a 75 MIP CISC speed requirement [2]) to hundreds or possibly thousands of fine nodes that are performing image processing at the pixel level. The 3-D computer under development by Hughes Research Laboratory, Malibu, California is an early example of the application of WSI in achieving these goals. [3]

Non-Availability of Avionics

As avionics become more complex, equipment failures and "soft" or anomalous failure continue to increase, thereby reducing the mission availability of the weapon system. Consider the following: avionics generally constitute 30-40% of the fly-away cost of modern fighter aircraft (\$15-35M a piece) and 35-50% of the total maintenance cost. The mean time between failure for mission critical avionics for the entire fighter weapon system is under ten hours (i.e. the aircraft will operate, on average, at a fully mission capable condition for say 6-8 hours).

It is imperative that overall avionics availability (e.g. reliability coupled with fault tolerance) be improved. In attempting to understand the role that WSI technology might play in helping achieve reliability improvements, it is useful to discuss the perceived cause of avionic failures.

First of all, it is important to note that a detailed understanding of failure causes and the physics of failure for military and civilian avionics is simply not available at this time. However, there is no dearth of "experts" willing to volunteer opinions concerning the major causes of failures. Further, much of the failure data we have is for the "last generation" technology and may not apply to modern day equipment.

For example, Air Force maintenance personnel working on electronics built in the 1960s and 1970s reported abnormally high rates of failure (e.g. 30-40%) due to cables and PWB connectors, yet, this data is still cited as being appropriate for modern day electronics. One estimate of the failure rate contribution of ICs for electronics of this era was about 2% (somewhat reflecting the limited use of ICs, but also reflecting the inherent reliability of microcircuitry). [4] Highly troubling however was the 1977 Boeing finding that 62% of the PWBs removed for replacement for A-6E and S-3 aircraft were found to be good parts. [4]

Figure 2, drawn from Reference [5], shows a break-out for avionics failure at the PWB level. For example, this study states that only 25% of the replaced parts failed due to primary failures, about 15% due to secondary failures and about 60% of the replaced parts were later declared as operating properly. (Note: This study considered components as well as PWBs as parts.) In addition, a high percentage of crew-reported avionics failures/anomalies cannot be duplicated at the flight line and no "black boxes" are pulled. The June 1988 report for F-16 avionics reports this rate at 28%. During the same time frame, 26% of F-16 avionics were labeled "bench check serviceable" at the intermediate shop at the military base. This means that for the black boxes that were pulled (based on BITE or some other trouble shooting procedure at the flight line), no problems could be found in one fourth the cases.

Figure 3, drawn from reference [5], depicts the results of a failure analysis which consolidated failure results from four avionics systems.

These systems were mid to late-1970s designs which are in the inventory today. One early (1971) study done by Grumman estimated that approximately 55% of the failures are caused by temperature extremes, 20% by vibration and 20% from humidity.

One immediately can draw the conclusion that ICs and hybrids have been steadily causing a higher percentage of actual failures, relative to discrete components, over the past two decades simply because the increased relative use of these devices. However, intrinsic reliability of microcircuitry (e.g. wear-out rate) is measured in decades of time. Therefore, achieving substantial reductions in avionics failure rates requires significantly improved thermal management, vibration isolation and hermetic sealing as we move to increased dependencies on hybrid multi-chip packages, hybrid wafers and monolithic wafers. (It must be remembered that military avionics will always experience relatively hostile operating conditions because of the missions, small available volume, weight, power and maintenance/support drawbacks.)

Returning to the issue of why (apparently) a high percentage of avionics maintenance actions do not involve actual parts failures, we will unfortunately have to fall back to expert opinion because no adequate data base has been developed. The consolidated view taken from designers and technicians is that there are several causes including: [6]

- 0 misdiagnosed wiring/connector problems resulting in good units being pulled
- 0 inadequate BITE coverage
- 0 power supply failure (also causing BITE failure)
- 0 poor maintenance procedures (e.g. "shotgun" removal of non-failed items)
- 0 software errors
- 0 operation at temperature extremes
- 0 poor solder joints

It is the latter category (solder joint problem) that has drawn the most discussion. Because of the subtle, insidious manner in which solder joint failures are manifested, failures become innately difficult to detect and, consequently, they may cause significant costs in trouble shooting, aircraft down time and additional spares to keep the logistics pipeline full. For example, if a weak chip-PWB solder joint passed inspection at the factory (latent defect), thermal cycling (CTE mismatch) and/or vibration may eventually cause an open circuit. When this happens in flight, the BITE may report a failure as having occurred someplace in the box. More thorough testing at the flight line, shop or depot may not reveal the problem because the vibration and/or the temperature has been removed.

It must first be acknowledged that extremely impressive reliability strides have been with microcircuitry, based on a "per function" level. For example, over the last 25 years, we have gone from 10 to 100,000 gates per chip while the reliability has increased 10 to 100 times for packaged semi-conductor chips, resulting in roughly a million times reliability per

function improvement. At the same time. . . "the gate to-pin ratio has increased from 0.1 to 1000, resulting in a drastic reduction in the historically less reliable pin connections to the PWB per circuit function. These improvements have been achieved by integrating more and more functions on the same chip and, thus, reducing the required packaging effort per function." [7]

Two major points need to be made that will affect the eventual use of WSI:

(1) We can expect a continued, and even escalated push for more and more functionality on future aircraft (i.e. to implement machine intelligence functions described above). Even assuming that chip and/or hybrid chip packages could be used to build flyable-sized super computers, increases in the number of solder joints will only exacerbate avionics failures and other associated problems. We need to substantially reduce/eliminate chip-level packaging and printed wiring boards if we are to achieve both increased functionality and reliability increases.

(2) Fundamental limits to current microcircuit design/processes prohibit continued reliability improvements. We are reaching feature size limits on chips due to attendant electromigration and manufacturing process defects that will begin introducing latent defects on the chip itself. Further, we are reaching pin out limits and will need to go to new interconnect technologies not only for reliability, but to more closely match "board" speed with chip speed. [7] By substantially reducing wire-lead capacitance and inductance through cell-to-cell interconnection on the wafer, much smaller driver circuits will be needed with an attendant reduction in cooling requirements (per function). And, by using photolithographic and laser trenching technologies for cell-to-cell interconnects, substantial improvements in interconnect reliability is expected.

The above trends point to the future need for WSI. There are several issues and problems however, some discussed below, which must be addressed before WSI becomes a practical approach for military electronics.

MILITARY AVIONICS PACKAGING/COOLING CONSIDERATIONS

New technologies, combined with growing maintenance/support costs have led the three military services to seriously consider the use of modular avionics. Through an advanced development program called PAVE PILLAR, the Avionics Laboratory is developing approximately 20 different module types for proof-of-concept demonstrations (e.g. data processors, signal processors, memory modules, power supplies, etc.).

For many avionics applications, the future use of WSI must be rationalized in the context of modular avionics. This portion of the paper will discuss the constraints imposed by modular avionics and will present a preliminary modular configuration. The modular concept depends on the use of a limited number of line replaceable modules (LRMs) which can be replaced at the flight line and directly sent to the depot, thereby eliminating the intermediate shop and its associated costs. (It appears that approximately one-third of the maintenance costs can be saved over a 20 year life cycle.) [8] One estimate of the number of LRMs for an advanced fighter aircraft application showed the need for the following:

<u>Module Type</u>	<u>Unique</u>	<u>Total</u>
Digital	25	350
Analog	50	100
Power Supply	10	80
	<u>85</u>	<u>530</u>

The concept of using LRMs for airborne functions was not practical until dense packaging was made possible by VLSI technology. (The U.S. Navy pioneered the use of LRMs for submarines and ship applications.) Central to the use of LRMs is improved BIT. Figure 4 shows a hierarchical test structure starting at the chip (where possible).

Figure 5 shows an artist's sketch of one design approach for typical VLSI module constructed with hermetically sealed multi-chip packages. (NOTE: A metallic cover encloses both sides for ease of handling and improved EMI protection.) The current circuitry uses chip and multi-chip packages solder bonded to a PWB located on either side of an aluminum heat sink which conducts heat to a rib. Heat is removed through a metal-to-metal pressure bond between the rib and a slot in the integrated rack. Liquid cooling in the rack transfers heat to an exchanger. For retrofit applications where cooling air is available, an air flow through a channel in the center of the module could be used to remove heat from PWBs on either side of the chamber. Module size is 6.4" x 5.88" with a 0.6 pitch. It is anticipated that approximately 40-50 watts can be removed from these modules while maintaining maximum junction temperatures around 80°C. A rib to maximum junction temperature difference of around 20°C is expected for chip and multi-chip hybrid packaging. Figure 6 shows a sketch of a multi-chip hybrid approach used with the LRM constraints. Solder connections have been estimated at around 2500 per module for data processing and 8000 per module for signal processing applications. This design represents 1990 available circuitry and should be considered a baseline from which WSI-based designs are compared. Figures 7 and 8 show projected characteristics of hybrid chip on board and monolithic wafer designs confined to LRM dimensions. Obviously, some form of advanced cooling must be employed.

It should also be noted that we can still exploit the inherent reliability of WSI and construct standard LRMs performing less demanding functions than robust parallel networks. For example, WSI would allow us to build an array of 16 bit or 32 bit data processors for "simple" parallel networks, extensive memory arrays or to even increase functional availability further by using spare cells on the wafer for fault tolerance.

Fundamentally, however, we must face the issue of whether we should continue to push both on-chip/cell technology (reduced feature size) and high density interconnection technology to their limits when building wafers. Here we are faced with a classical design trade-off which involves several factors. For example, since achieving high yield is a dominant requirement for WSI, we must seek a balance between cell/interconnection technologies. The processes which are used to build both dense cell structures and interconnects must be evaluated to determine if inherent latent defects are being "built into" the manufacturing process which will cause failures under adverse military avionics environments. A balanced design approach that includes applications requirements, yield, packaging/cooling limitations and reliability must be developed. In some instances, "low" technology (e.g. 3 micron feature size/ 8 MHz clock) which provide excellent yield and low power dissipation may be totally appropriate, particularly if parallelism can make up the "difference" in speed. The Hughes' Research Laboratory "3-D" computer is an excellent example of this approach. [3] Also, the

characteristics of the application algorithm will determine whether a stacked wafer or single wafer design is appropriate. For simple processing requiring robust, fine grain parallelism (e.g. ATR, image processing), a 3-D design allows simple wafers to be built without the need for high density interconnects on the wafer. Here, data communications occur between I/O, CPU and memory cells located on a vertical axis across several wafers. For complex algorithms requiring logic manipulations and extensive data retrieval (e.g. control, expert system processing), high density interconnections across the wafer is required. However, if it results that extensive heat removal (e.g. greater than 75 watts) is required for LRM-size modules to achieve reliable operation, advanced cooling designs must be considered. In addition wafer-to-wafer interconnections may present potential problems in reliability, bandwidth and EMI susceptibility. Figure 9 shows an artists sketch of an advanced design which incorporates photonics

(fiberoptics, optical wave guides) for both a rack and conformal package configuration. Also, the lower right portion of Figure 9 shows an approach to achieving flow through immersion cooling for improved heat removal.

WSI IMPACT ON FUTURE AVIONICS

The above discussion hopefully establishes potential benefits of WSI in improving avionics reliability and enabling extremely high speed data, image, signal and heuristic processing for improved performance. It is worth-while to consider the broader issue of how WSI might impact overall avionic system architectures and functional integration. Although space does not permit details to be provided, the authors believe that the extreme processing speeds enabled by WSI will allow and promote the further integration and fusion of sensor data on future aircraft.

High speed (5-10 BOP) WSI based signal processors will allow radio frequency (RF) functions across the entire spectrum will become more tightly coupled. For example, radar and electronic warfare threat detection may merge, allowing the use of the same antenna. Eventually, a WSI-based "RF metafunction" is predicted where RF bands and antennas are shared between classical radar, communications, IFF, threat warning and radio navigation (e.g. GPS, TACAN). Reduced weight, volume, power and improved performance are expected. Similarly, metafunctions are expected to evolve in the areas of crew station processing, system control/decision making (e.g. cooperating expert systems), electro-optical sensors and integrated flight/fire/propulsion control.

WSI EXPLOITATION PLANS

The Avionics Laboratory is currently planning an Advanced Development Program called PAVE PACE. This effort is aimed at exploiting technology strides in microcircuitry, photonics, packaging/cooling, parallel processing and software development environments and building an advanced avionic hardware and software infrastructure for early 21st century avionics. Goals include: improving real-time avionic processing speeds by 100-1000, improving avionic system reliability to 250 hours and improving software productivity by a factor of 2-5.

WSI technology will be carefully investigated to determine its role in building highly reliable and high speed parallel processors. After an initial PAVE PACE architecture design and specification effort beginning in 1990, it is anticipated that hardware development would begin in about 1993. Hopefully, WSI issues, particularly those connected with yield, will be resolved by then.

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HIGH SPEED COMPUTING PROVIDES FORCE MULTIPLICATION THROUGH MACHINE INTELLIGENCE

Figure 1

Figure 2

APPROXIMATE FAILURE RATE OF 1970's AVIONICS

Figure 3

MODULAR AVIONICS STRUCTURE

Figure 4

ITEM	1990 TIMEFRAME
* % SILICON	20%
CLOCK RATE	20-25 MHz
* CHIP SIZE (INCH)	0.4-0.6
* GATES PER CHIP	50-25K
* SUBSTRATE SIZE (INCHES)	2 x 4
* LINE WIDTH AND SPACING (MILS)	1.5/1.3
* PAD SIZE AND SPACING (MILS)	3.4/1.2
* SYSTEM THROUGHPUT	450 MOPS/125 MFLOPS
* MEMORY SIZE	DRAM 256 Kb-1 Mb SRAM 64-256 Kb
* POWER DISSIPATION	25 WATTS

MULTI CHIP HYBRID PROCESSING ELEMENTS

Figure 5

TYPICAL LRM CONFIGURATION

Figure 6

ITEM		1995 TIMEFRAME
• % SILICON		50%
CLOCK RATE		20-25 MHz
• CHIP SIZE (INCH)		0.8
• GATES PER CHIP		1000K
• SUBSTRATE SIZE (INCHES)		4 x 4
• LINE WIDTH AND SPACING (MILS)		0.5-1.0/0.5-1.0
• PAD SIZE AND SPACING (MILS)		0.5-1.0/0.5-1.0
• SYSTEM THROUGHPUT		1.2 BOPS/1 BFLOPS
• MEMORY SIZE	DRAM	1-16 Mb
	SRAM	256 Kb-1 Mb
• POWER DISSIPATION		100-200 WATTS

PROCESSING ELEMENTS
SEALED CHIP ON BOARD

Figure 7

ITEM		2000 TIMEFRAME
• % SILICON		100%
CLOCK RATE		25-250 MHz
• SIZE		4 x 4
• LINE WIDTH AND SPACING (MILS)		<0.5
• PAD SIZE AND SPACING (MILS)		<0.5
• SYSTEM THROUGHPUT		30* BOPS/15* BFLOPS
• EMBEDDED MEMORY	DRAM	TBD
	SRAM	TBD
• POWER DISSIPATION		200* WATTS

WAFER SCALE INTEGRATION
PROCESSING ELEMENT

Figure 8

OPTOELECTRONIC TECHNOLOGY
ENHANCES ADVANCED AVIONICS
INSTALLATIONS

Figure 9